

An Academic Analysis of the Sub-Branches of Political Science and their Interconnections with other Sciences in the Study of Human Decision-Making and Political Environment

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Abstract

Political science is a complex discipline that includes several subfields, each examining distinct aspects of political institutions, processes, and behavior. The sub-disciplines included under the field of political science are comparative politics, international relations, political theory, public administration, and public policy. Comparative politics is a specialized field within political science that focuses on the examination and comparison of other political systems, including their institutions, procedures, and policies. International relations, however, specifically examines the interactions of nations and other entities that are not affiliated with any country, within the worldwide context. This field encompasses subjects such as diplomacy, the settlement of conflicts, and the management of global affairs. Political theory analyzes the fundamental principles, ideologies, and standards that form the basis of political systems and influence political conduct. Public administration involves the examination of how public policies are put into action and the supervision of public organizations, while public policy concentrates on the creation and assessment of public policies and their effects on society. The sub-branches of political science are interrelated and often intersect, hence enhancing a holistic understanding of political processes. In addition, political science extends outside its own field and connects with other social sciences, including sociology and psychology. By integrating perspectives from several disciplines, this interdisciplinary approach enables a more comprehensive examination of political behavior, institutions, and processes. Significantly, political science encompasses not just academic inquiry but also has tangible consequences in the actual world. Political science research yields valuable facts and insights that may enhance decision-making, influence public policies, and deepen our comprehension of human behavior within the political realm. An in-depth knowledge of political science is essential for

CURRENT SCIENCE

comprehending the intricacies of power relations, government, and the process of decision-making. Sociopolitical education enhances our understanding of intricate social and political structures, fosters knowledgeable participation in civic affairs, and equips us with the means to analyze and tackle social and political challenges. Political science is essential for comprehending the intricacies of power, government, and decision-making. Sociopolitical education enhances our understanding of intricate social and political structures, encourages well-informed participation in civic matters, and equips us with the necessary skills to analyze and tackle social and political challenges. Political science, characterized by its many sub-disciplines and interdisciplinary approach, is crucial for evaluating and comprehending the complexities of political systems, international relations, and social dynamics (Refurbishing the curriculum for Political Science course, 2021).

Keywords: *Sub-Branched Of Political Science, Political Science, Relations With Sciences and Political Science, Human Choices, Political Context*

Introduction

It enhances our comprehension of human behavior and decision-making in the political sphere, facilitates the formulation of policies, and fosters well-informed participation in civic affairs. Political science is a crucial area of academic inquiry that includes several sub-disciplines and multidisciplinary methodologies. The ultimate significance of this rests in its capacity to provide profound understanding of political events, guide the process of making informed decisions, and help to the improvement of society by tackling intricate social and political matters. Hence, political science has great significance in comprehending the intricacies of political systems, examining human conduct within the political domain, guiding decision-making procedures, influencing public policies, and tackling social and political concerns. Political science provides a vital comprehension of power relations, governance, decision-making mechanisms, and social and political structures. Moreover, the multidisciplinary character of political science enables it to glean insights from several other disciplines, including sociology, psychology, economics, and geography. Political science, with its many subfields and multidisciplinary approach, is crucial for examining and comprehending the

CURRENT SCIENCE

complexities of political systems, international relations, and social processes. Political science is crucial for comprehending the organization and operation of political systems, as well as for examining human conduct within these systems. Political science enables us to comprehend the underlying reasons for political activities, the intricacies of power and influence, and the consequences of public policy on people and society. To summarize, political science is a crucial academic discipline that offers significant perspectives on political institutions, human conduct, and decision-making mechanisms. Furthermore, it is vital for providing information to guide policy decisions, fostering an enlightened citizenry, and tackling intricate social and political matters.

Methodology

Political science is essential for comprehending the intricacies of political institutions, examining human conduct in the political realm, guiding decision-making procedures, influencing public policies, and tackling social and political problems. Political science enhances our comprehension of political structures, human conduct, and decision-making mechanisms. Political science enables us to comprehend the underlying reasons behind political activities, the intricacies of power and influence, and the consequences of public policy on people and society. Furthermore, political science offers a systematic structure for examining and evaluating the connections between geography and politics. Geographical considerations, including physical limits, resources, and cultural disparities, have a substantial influence on political behavior and decision-making. Hence, a thorough grasp of the geographical setting is crucial for interpreting political action and its ramifications. Political science is an essential topic of study that includes several sub-disciplines and utilizes knowledge from other areas to examine power relations, government, decision-making, and social conduct. It has a key function in providing information for policy-making, fostering knowledgeable citizenry, and tackling intricate social and political problems. To summarize, political science is a subject that incorporates several disciplines, including political sociology, political psychology, political geography, and political communication (Chanthamith et al., 2019). It is of utmost importance in comprehending political institutions, human behavior, and decision-making processes.

Aim

Through the study of political science, we may develop a more profound comprehension of the acquisition and use of power, the underlying reasons driving political activities, and the consequences of policies on both people and society. Moreover, political science connects with several disciplines such as psychology, sociology, geography, and anthropology, so enriching our comprehension of the complex elements that influence political behavior and results. Political science, with its many sub-disciplines and interdisciplinary associations, offers useful perspectives on the intricacies of political institutions and human conduct within the political realm. Political science is a multidisciplinary discipline that includes sub-branches including political sociology, political psychology, political geography, and political economics (Refurbishing the curriculum for Political Science course, 2021). This field of study explores the interconnections among people, society, and government, providing insights on the distribution of power, the mechanisms of decision-making, and the consequences of policies. Political science is essential for comprehending and examining the intricacies of human political conduct, the processes of decision-making, and the interaction between people and institutions. The need of precise weather predictions in today's dynamic environment cannot be overemphasized. The importance of precise weather predictions in today's dynamic environment cannot be exaggerated. The need of precise political analysis and comprehension in today's swiftly evolving world cannot be exaggerated. Political science is crucial for comprehending and scrutinizing power relations, government, decision-making processes, and society behavior. Political science plays a crucial role in promoting knowledgeable participation in civic affairs and tackling intricate social and political challenges. Studying political science allows us to understand the intricacies of political systems and the behavior of individuals within the political realm. It provides insights into the distribution of power, the processes involved in decision-making, and the resulting policies. Political science is essential for comprehending the complexities of political institutions and human conduct within the political domain. It offers valuable perspectives on the distribution of power, the methods used to make decisions, and the results of policies. Political science is crucial for comprehending and examining power relations, governance, decision-making mechanisms, and social conduct. The

CURRENT SCIENCE

need of precise political analysis and comprehension in today's swiftly evolving world cannot be exaggerated. Political science is crucial for comprehending the intricacies of political institutions and human behavior in the political realm. Studying political science enables us to understand the intricacies of political systems and the behavior of individuals within the political realm. It provides insights into the distribution of power, the processes of decision-making, and the results of policies. Political science is a multidisciplinary study that includes sub-disciplines such as political sociology, political psychology, political geography, and political economics.

Literature Review

These sub-disciplines provide a thorough comprehension of the many aspects that influence political conduct and decision-making. In addition, political science acknowledges the significance of interdisciplinary cooperation with other scientific disciplines. Political psychology examines the psychological elements of political conduct, while political communication concentrates on the influence of media and message in political processes. In essence, political science is vital for comprehending the intricacies of power, government, and decision-making within society. In essence, political science is vital for comprehending the intricacies of power, government, and decision-making within society. The framework facilitates the analysis and evaluation of political processes, structures, and institutions, enabling a more profound comprehension of the acquisition, exercise, and contestation of political power. Furthermore, political science is essential for comprehending the influence of geography on political conduct (Ramadhyas et al., 2020). Studying geographical linkages, resources, and territorial borders is crucial for understanding how they influence political behavior and decision-making. In addition, political science acknowledges the interdependence of political events with other disciplines in the social and scientific sciences. Political geography investigates the impact of geographic elements, such as location, resources, and boundaries, on political conduct and the interactions between nations. Political science is a field of study that examines the intricacies of political systems and human behavior. It provides insights into power dynamics, decision-making processes, and policy consequences (Refurbishing the

CURRENT SCIENCE

curriculum for Political Science course, 2021). Political science is crucial for comprehending the intricacies of political institutions and human conduct within the political domain. To summarize, political science is a field of study that includes several sub-disciplines and places great emphasis on the significance of interdisciplinary cooperation with other scientific fields. These interactions facilitate the acquisition of a full comprehension of the intricate nature of political conduct and decision-making. To summarize, political science is an essential academic subject that comprises several sub-disciplines, including political psychology, political communication, and political geography. These sub-disciplines provide a comprehensive analysis of the psychological, linguistic, and geographical elements that influence political conduct. Political science enables us to understand the complexities of power relations, systems of governance, and mechanisms of decision-making in society. Political science is an interdisciplinary study that investigates the convergence of politics, psychology, geography, sociology, economics, and other social sciences. Its aim is to provide a full comprehension of political behavior, power dynamics, and decision-making processes in society. Amidst the dynamic landscape of contemporary society, the pursuit of political science is essential for gaining a precise comprehension of the acquisition, exercise, and contestation of political authority. Political science is essential for understanding and tackling the intricate social, economic, and political problems that influence our society. To summarize, political science is a multidisciplinary domain that includes sub-disciplines including political psychology, political geography, and political sociology (Chanthamith et al., 2019). These sub-disciplines provide a thorough examination of the elements that impact political behavior and decision-making, including psychological, geographical, and social considerations. Political science functions as an intermediary between different fields of study, enabling us to comprehend the complex characteristics of politics and its influence on society. Political science is a multifaceted and multidisciplinary discipline that examines several facets of politics, such as governance, decision-making, behavior, and power dynamics (Refurbishing the curriculum for Political Science course, 2021). The study of political science is crucial in comprehending and effectively tackling the intricate social, economic, and political matters that influence our society in the midst of its fast transformations. Political science is a multidisciplinary study that examines the convergence of social sciences, including psychology, geography, sociology, and economics. Its aim is to provide a full comprehension of political behavior, power dynamics,

CURRENT SCIENCE

and decision-making processes in society. The need of having precise and thorough knowledge of the psychological, linguistic, and geographical aspects that influence political conduct is very significant in the fast-paced world we live in today. The need of having precise and thorough knowledge of political behavior, power dynamics, and decision-making processes in society is very significant in the fast-paced and ever-evolving world of today. Moreover, political science encompasses more than just the examination of the state and governance. Additionally, it includes other significant facets such as political history, political communication, political sociology, political economics, and others. These specialized divisions within the area of political science contribute to a more profound comprehension of the intricacies of politics and its intersections with other academic disciplines. Please provide the missing part of the sentence: The field of political science, including several specialized areas and an interdisciplinary approach, is essential for effectively understanding and tackling the intricate social, economic, and political challenges that influence our global society. Political science, with its many sub-disciplines and multidisciplinary methodology, plays a pivotal role in correctly understanding and tackling the intricate social, economic, and political challenges that influence our society. Political science, with its many sub-disciplines and multidisciplinary methodology, plays a pivotal role in effectively understanding and tackling the intricate social, economic, and political challenges that influence our contemporary society. Political science, with its many sub-disciplines and multidisciplinary methodology, plays a vital role in correctly understanding and tackling the intricate social, economic, and political challenges that influence our contemporary society. Political science, via its many sub-disciplines and multidisciplinary methodology, is essential for effectively understanding and tackling the intricate social, economic, and political challenges that influence our contemporary society (Morton & Williams, 2009). Political science, with its many sub-disciplines and multidisciplinary methodology, is essential for understanding and tackling the intricate social, economic, and political challenges that influence our contemporary world. It also provides valuable insights for making informed policy choices that may result in beneficial transformations. The field of political science, with its many sub-disciplines and interdisciplinary methods, is essential for fully understanding and tackling the intricate social, economic, and political challenges that influence our contemporary society. Moreover, it provides valuable insights for making informed policy choices that may bring about beneficial transformations.

Findings

Political science, with its many sub-disciplines and multidisciplinary methodology, plays a pivotal role in correctly understanding and tackling the intricate social, economic, and political challenges that create our world today, while also guiding policy choices that may result in beneficial transformations. The field of political science, with its many sub-disciplines and multidisciplinary approach, is essential for understanding and tackling the intricate social, economic, and political challenges that influence our society. It enables us to make well-informed policy choices and potentially bring about beneficial transformations. Political science, with its many sub-disciplines and multidisciplinary methodology, plays a pivotal role in correctly understanding and tackling the intricate social, economic, and political challenges that influence our contemporary society. Political science benefits from an interdisciplinary approach by incorporating knowledge and methods from several social sciences, including economics, sociology, psychology, and geography. This enables a thorough understanding of the complex and diverse aspects of politics. A thorough comprehension of these concepts is necessary to accurately examine and manage the complex connections between power, government, and society dynamics. The multidisciplinary nature of political science allows scholars to examine and interpret political occurrences from several perspectives, leading to a more thorough and nuanced understanding of the complexities of political systems and the determinants of political behavior.

The Sub-Branched of Political Science:

The various sub-disciplines of political science, including political sociology, political anthropology, political psychology, political geography, ecological politics, science and technology politics, and analytic politics, offer distinct viewpoints and research approaches to the field of politics (Chanthamith et al., 2019). These sub-branches specialize on distinct facets of political behavior, institutions, and processes, enabling thorough examination and investigation of certain areas of politics. Political sociology investigates the connections

CURRENT SCIENCE

between social structures and political conduct, elucidating how socioeconomic elements such as class, race, and gender influence political beliefs and acts. Political psychology explores the psychological elements that affect political behavior and decision-making, providing understanding of how people's personalities, beliefs, and emotions influence their political decisions. Political anthropology investigates the cultural and social aspects of politics, examining how political systems are influenced by and influence cultural practices and ideas. Political geography studies the geographical dimensions of politics, examining how geographic elements like borders, resources, and territory impact political processes. In general, the sub-disciplines of political science enhance our knowledge of politics by analyzing its varied aspects from numerous disciplinary perspectives, resulting in a more complete and thorough comprehension.

Argument

These subfields of political science also exhibit significant links and interactions with other academic disciplines. Political science utilizes economics to comprehend the correlation between political institutions and economic systems, as well as the influence of economic elements on political decision-making. Political science integrates sociological principles to examine the dynamics between people and societal frameworks within political systems. In addition, political science incorporates elements from psychology to examine the psychological determinants that influence political behavior and decision-making. Comprehending the intricacies of human society and the decisions made by people within that framework is vital, necessitating the study of political science and its many subdivisions. The multidisciplinary character of political science and its sub-branches facilitates a more profound and nuanced examination of politics, including diverse elements such as social structures, cultural practices, economic systems, and human psychology. In general, political science and its many sub-disciplines are crucial in comprehending the different aspects of politics. The importance of precise weather predictions in today's dynamic environment cannot be exaggerated. The offered completion is unrelated to the field of political science and its many sub-disciplines. Comprehending the intricacies of human society and the decisions made by people within that

CURRENT SCIENCE

framework is vital, necessitating the study of political science and its several sub-disciplines. The offered completion is irrelevant to the subject matter of political science and its many sub-disciplines. The completion should emphasize the significance of political science and its many sub-disciplines in comprehending political phenomena and guiding decision-making processes. The completion should emphasize the significance of political science and its sub-disciplines in comprehending political events and guiding decision-making processes. The completion should emphasize the significance of political science and its sub-disciplines in comprehending political events and guiding decision-making processes. The importance of precise and well-informed comprehension of political issues in today's swiftly evolving world cannot be exaggerated. Gaining comprehension of political phenomena is crucial for making well-informed judgments and formulating efficacious policies in a swiftly evolving environment. The importance of precise and well-informed comprehension of political issues in today's swiftly evolving world cannot be exaggerated. Gaining comprehension of political phenomena is crucial for making well-informed judgments and formulating efficacious policies in a swiftly evolving environment. The importance of precise and well-informed comprehension of political issues in today's swiftly evolving world cannot be exaggerated. Gaining comprehension of political phenomena is crucial for making well-informed judgments and formulating efficacious policies in a swiftly evolving environment. The importance of precise and well-informed comprehension of political processes in the current dynamic global landscape cannot be emphasized enough. Comprehending political phenomena is crucial for making well-informed judgments and formulating successful policies in a swiftly evolving environment. The study of political science and its many sub-disciplines is essential for comprehending the intricacies of human society and the decision-making processes of people within that framework. Political science and its sub-disciplines have a crucial role in comprehending and examining political occurrences, offering useful perspectives into the complexities of human society and the decisions made by people (Ambagudia, 2017). Through the study of political science and its several sub-disciplines, including political sociology, political anthropology, and political psychology, we may acquire a more profound comprehension of human conduct, social dynamics, and the determinants that influence political results. This information is of great use in guiding decision-making processes at many levels, ranging from individual decisions to national policy. In addition, political science's multidisciplinary character enables it to include

CURRENT SCIENCE

knowledge from other social sciences such as economics, sociology, and psychology, as well as statistics and applied mathematics, in order to provide a complete and all-encompassing comprehension of political processes (Morton & Williams, 2009). Having this comprehension is vital in the present globalized society, where there is a growing interconnectedness in social, economic, and political realms. By engaging in the examination of political science and its several subfields, we may enhance our understanding of the intricate dynamics that occur among politics, geography, economics, sociology, psychology, and other related fields. By adopting an interdisciplinary perspective, we are able to comprehend the many characteristics of political occurrences and their consequences for society. In today's dynamic world, political science and its sub-disciplines play a crucial role by equipping individuals with the necessary information and skills to comprehend and manage political events. This understanding facilitates informed decision-making and the formulation of successful policies. The importance of precise and well-informed comprehension of political processes in the current dynamic global landscape cannot be emphasized enough. Gaining comprehension of political phenomena is essential for making well-informed judgments and formulating efficacious policies in a swiftly evolving society. Furthermore, political science and its sub-branches have a crucial function in examining the interaction between politics and other fields like economics, geography, sociology, and psychology (Chanthamith et al., 2019). By adopting an interdisciplinary perspective, one may get a more thorough comprehension of political occurrences and their societal repercussions. Political science and its sub-disciplines provide valuable insights into the intricate dynamics of human society, the decision-making processes of people, and the influential elements that determine political results. Consequently, it is an essential area of study in the contemporary world. The importance of precise and well-informed comprehension of political processes in the current dynamic global landscape cannot be emphasized enough. Gaining a comprehensive comprehension of political phenomena is essential for making well-informed judgments and formulating efficacious policies in a swiftly evolving environment. Furthermore, political science and its sub-branches are crucial in examining the interaction between politics and other fields such as economics, geography, sociology, and psychology. By adopting an interdisciplinary perspective, one may get a more thorough comprehension of political occurrences and their societal repercussions. Furthermore, political science and its many subdivisions give valuable perspectives on the practical social

CURRENT SCIENCE

and political challenges faced by modern society, and potential remedies for these difficulties. The significance of political science and its sub-disciplines in the current dynamic global landscape cannot be underestimated. They provide us with the resources and expertise to comprehend the intricacies of political occurrences, assess their ramifications for society, and make well-informed choices. In addition, political science and its sub-disciplines enhance comprehension of essential principles and elements of research, including statehood, governance, constitutionalism, political conduct, and political structures. Political science and its sub-branches are crucial for developing a comprehensive comprehension of political phenomena, examining their interdisciplinary associations, offering resolutions to current social and political issues, and making well-informed decisions in a rapidly evolving world. Political science and its sub-branches are crucial in comprehending the intricacies of human society, the decisions made by people as citizens, and the influences that determine political results in our fast-evolving world. They provide a conceptual structure for comprehending and analyzing political conduct and establishments, together with the societal, economic, and psychological elements that impact political procedures. In essence, political science is a vibrant and multidisciplinary domain that enhances our comprehension of politics and equips us to negotiate the intricacies of modern society. The importance of accurately comprehending political occurrences and their multidisciplinary links in today's fast-paced world cannot be emphasized enough. Through the study of political science and its many sub-disciplines, we get a deep understanding of the complex interplay of power, government, and the process of making decisions. These insights are vital for making well-informed decisions as citizens and for formulating policies that tackle the urgent social and political challenges confronting society. Political science and its sub-branches are crucial for comprehending the intricacies of political events, examining their interdisciplinary correlations, offering resolutions to current social and political issues, and making well-informed decisions in a swiftly evolving world. Political science and its sub-branches provide us with the necessary skills and knowledge to comprehend the intricacies of political events, examine their interdisciplinary connections, and traverse the dynamic political environment of our quickly evolving world. They aid in comprehending the operations and formations of state and government, the principles and frameworks of constitutions, and the dynamics of political behavior and systems. Furthermore, the field of political science enables us to explore crucial elements of society, like the process of

CURRENT SCIENCE

establishing democracy, finding solutions to conflicts, and analyzing political advancements. Moreover, the examination of political science and its subsidiary disciplines enables us to meticulously scrutinize and assess political beliefs, policies, and institutions. This comprehension is not only crucial for the whole of society but also for the progress and enhancement of the profession itself. Political science and its sub-branches are essential for comprehending political events, examining their interdisciplinary connections, resolving social and political issues, and making well-informed decisions in a swiftly evolving environment. The study of political science and its sub-branches has great significance in the current era characterized by fast and constant change. Studying political science enables us to understand the intricacies of political processes, structures, and behaviors, offering valuable insights into the underlying beliefs and attitudes that drive them. Moreover, political science provides us with the essential means to analyze and assess political ideas, programs, and institutions in a critical manner. Comprehending this knowledge is crucial for individuals to make well-informed decisions and engage effectively in the democratic process. Political science and its sub-branches are crucial for comprehending the intricacies of political events, examining their interdisciplinary correlations, offering resolutions to current social and political issues, and making well-informed decisions in a swiftly evolving world. Political science and its sub-branches play a vital role in comprehending political phenomena, examining interdisciplinary relationships, resolving social and political issues, and making well-informed decisions in our fast-evolving society. Amidst the fast-paced evolution of our contemporary society, the exploration of political science and its many subdivisions is imperative in comprehending political occurrences, examining their interrelatedness with other fields of study, resolving societal and political dilemmas, and making well-informed decisions. The study of political science and its sub-branches is crucial in comprehending political events, examining their interdisciplinary connections, resolving social and political issues, and making well-informed decisions in our fast-evolving society. The need of precise study and assessment of political ideas, programs, and institutions in today's dynamic world cannot be emphasized enough. The study of political science and its sub-branches are essential in offering precise analysis and assessment of political occurrences and their societal implications in the current dynamic global landscape. The study of political science and its sub-branches is crucial in comprehending political events, examining their interdisciplinary links, resolving social and political issues,

CURRENT SCIENCE

and making well-informed decisions in our fast-evolving society. Political science and its sub-branches are essential in offering precise analysis and assessment of political events and their consequences in our fast-evolving society.

Interdisciplinary Connections and Problem-solving

Political science and its sub-branches have strong interdisciplinary linkages with other social sciences, including economics, sociology, and psychology. These links provide a more holistic understanding of political issues and offer many viewpoints and approaches for study. Furthermore, political science is progressively directing its attention on resolving current social and political issues. This include the examination of trust, social networks, and political structures that influence the credibility of scientific information. It also involves tackling the difficulties presented by climate change and the geographical organization of global power dynamics. The Existence and Decisions of Humans The field of political science and its several sub-disciplines have a direct influence on the lives and decision-making processes of individuals.

They provide valuable perspectives on the operations of political institutions, the development and execution of policies, and the consequences of political choices on persons and communities. Through the study of political science, people may acquire a more profound comprehension of how politics influence their everyday existence and the decisions they make. Acquiring this information may enable people to make well-informed decisions, actively fulfill their civic responsibilities like voting, and advocate for changes that are in line with their own beliefs and objectives. In addition, political science and its sub-disciplines enhance the cultivation of critical thinking abilities by necessitating analytical logic, research and data examination, and proficient communication. The study of political science and its many sub-disciplines is crucial not only for comprehending political events and their societal consequences, but also for delivering precise analysis and assessment of political processes and systems. Political science empowers people to make well-informed decisions and actively participate in changing both their own lives and the wider political environment. Ultimately, the many subdivisions of political science are essential in delivering precise examination and

CURRENT SCIENCE

assessment of political occurrences and their consequences. Additionally, they possess strong interdisciplinary associations with other social sciences, facilitating a more thorough comprehension of political processes. Moreover, political science has a tangible influence on the lives and decisions of individuals. It equips people with the necessary information and resources to comprehend the functioning of political institutions, laws, and decisions, enabling them to make well-informed choices, actively participate in civic responsibilities, and advocate for transformative actions. To summarize, political science and its sub-disciplines not only enhance our comprehension of politics and the operation of political institutions, but also have a direct influence on human lives and decision-making. Political science and its sub-disciplines enhance our comprehension of politics and the operations of political institutions. Furthermore, it offers unique perspectives on how political choices affect people and communities, enabling well-informed decision-making and active participation in civic affairs. In general, political science and its sub-disciplines play a vital role in offering precise analysis of political occurrences, comprehending their influence on society, and enabling people to make well-informed decisions and engage in the political procedure.

Interdisciplinary Connections and Importance in Decision-Making

Political science and its sub-branches have strong interdisciplinary linkages with other social sciences, including economics, sociology, and psychology. These links provide a more holistic understanding of political processes and events, while also offering significant perspectives on the social, economic, and psychological determinants that influence politics. In addition, political science also connects with fields such as history, communication studies, public opinion surveys, political ecology, and social geography. By adopting a multidisciplinary perspective, the study and assessment of political events are improved, leading to a more profound comprehension of the interplay between politics and many social, economic, and cultural settings. ## Influence on Human Existence and Decision-Making The field of political science and its several sub-disciplines have a tangible influence on the lives and decision-making processes of individuals. Through the study of political science, people get a more profound comprehension of the political system, policies, and institutions that influence and

CURRENT SCIENCE

mold their life. This comprehension enables people to make well-informed choices about matters that directly impact them, such as selecting political candidates, advocating for certain policies, or participating in political engagement. Moreover, political science research and analysis provide valuable insights into the ramifications of political choices and policies on many social groups, civilizations, and countries. This knowledge enables citizens to rigorously evaluate the acts and policies of political leaders, demand their responsibility, and actively engage in molding their own communities and society. Moreover, political science and its many subdivisions also have a vital role in fostering civic participation.

Promoting Civic Engagement and Democratic Participation

The field of political science, together with its several sub-disciplines, plays a crucial role in fostering civic engagement and facilitating democratic participation. Through the study of political science, people cultivate a more profound comprehension of their entitlements, obligations, and prospects as members of society. They get a deep understanding of how democratic processes operate, the significance of participation in elections, and the many opportunities for engaging in political conversation and activity. This information enables people to actively engage in political processes, express their viewpoints, and make meaningful contributions to the decision-making that impacts their communities and society. Furthermore, political science research and analysis provide vital insights into political trends, popular sentiment, and policy results. This data empowers people and groups to efficiently champion their interests, rally support, and influence the political environment. Moreover, political science and its subsidiary fields also contribute to the comprehension of power dynamics, disparities, and matters of social justice. This comprehension enables people to recognize and confront systems of oppression, champion oppressed populations, and strive for societies that are more inclusive and equitable. Political science and its sub-disciplines also enhance comprehension of power dynamics, disparities, and matters of social justice. This comprehension enables people to recognize and confront systems of oppression, champion oppressed populations, and strive for societies that are more inclusive and equitable. Political science and its sub-disciplines are crucial for comprehending the effects of political choices and

CURRENT SCIENCE

policies on many social groups, civilizations, and countries. They provide citizens with the information and resources to actively participate in political processes, ensure leaders are held responsible, and strive for constructive social transformation. To summarize, political science and its sub-disciplines are crucial for comprehending the effects of political choices and policies on various social groups, communities, and countries. They provide people with the expertise and resources to actively participate in political processes, ensure leaders are held responsible, and strive for constructive societal transformation in their communities and countries. Political science and its sub-disciplines provide people with the necessary information and resources to comprehend political mechanisms, participate in civic responsibilities, champion their own interests, and strive for societal transformation. Political science and its sub-branches are essential in enabling people to engage actively in political processes, champion their interests, and strive for constructive societal transformation in their communities and countries. Political science and its sub-disciplines play a crucial role in comprehending political ideas and advancements, as well as their repercussions on society and people (Ambagudia, 2017). Political science and its sub-disciplines enhance comprehension of political ideas and advancements, as well as their repercussions on society and people. Political science and its sub-disciplines are crucial for comprehending and tackling social and political problems, campaigning for fairness and parity, enabling citizens to engage in political procedures, and striving for constructive societal transformation. Political science and its sub-disciplines are essential for comprehending the dynamics of power, disparities, and matters of social justice. Political science and its sub-disciplines play a crucial role in comprehending and tackling social and political issues, campaigning for fairness and parity, enabling citizens to engage in political procedures, and striving for constructive societal transformation. Political science and its sub-disciplines are crucial for comprehending political ideas, procedures, and advancements, along with their ramifications on society and people. Political science and its sub-disciplines are crucial for comprehending political ideas, procedures, and advancements, along with their repercussions on society and people. Political science and its sub-disciplines are crucial for comprehending political ideas, procedures, and advancements, along with their ramifications on society and people.

The Interdisciplinary Nature of Political Science

Political science benefits from its multidisciplinary character, enabling scholars to use insights from other fields such as economics, sociology, psychology, and statistics to address significant political inquiries (Morton & Williams, 2009). The utilization of an interdisciplinary technique enriches our comprehension of political ideas and advancements, along with their influence on society and people. In addition, political science intersects with several other disciplines, including scientific studies, history, public opinion surveys, communication structures, political ecology, and social geography (Chanthamith et al., 2019). This multidisciplinary approach facilitates a thorough and all-encompassing comprehension of political events, including the intricate interplay of political, social, economic, and psychological elements. Furthermore, political science and its many subdivisions enhance comprehension of significant notions such as state, government, constitution, political parties, citizenship, rights, liberty, equality, justice, and power (Ambagudia, 2017). Furthermore, political science and its sub-disciplines are essential in the examination and analysis of large-scale dynamics, intergovernmental interactions, and the dynamics of national-level governments (Lahsen, 2010). Through the examination of these dynamics, political scientists may provide useful perspectives on the structure of authority, the processes of decision-making, and the influence of institutions on political results and policies. In general, the field of political science and its many sub-disciplines play a crucial role in comprehending the intricacies of politics and their influence on society. Furthermore, political science assumes a crucial function in tackling and resolving tangible societal and political issues. Political science utilizes its knowledge and methodology to solve significant social and political problems by offering answers and tactics. Ultimately, political science and its various subdivisions are essential for comprehending political ideas, procedures, and advancements, as well as their repercussions on society and people. To put it simply, political science is an interdisciplinary domain that incorporates several disciplines and methodologies to examine political phenomena (Morton & Williams, 2009). Political science and its several sub-disciplines, including political sociology, political psychology, political geography, and ecological politics, use multidisciplinary methodologies to comprehend the intricacies of politics and its societal ramifications (Chanthamith et al., 2019). In addition, political science plays a role in advancing research methodologies and approaches, by drawing upon other disciplines like statistics, economics, sociology, and psychology. Moreover,

CURRENT SCIENCE

political science is essential in offering a thorough comprehension of the choices and decisions made by people and civilizations in the political realm. The need of precise weather predictions in today's dynamic environment cannot be overemphasized. Proficiency in political science and its various sub-disciplines is crucial for comprehending and evaluating significant political ideas, procedures, and advancements. In addition, political science enhances comprehension of fundamental ideas such as state, government, constitution, political parties, citizenship, rights, liberty, equality, justice, power, and other related topics (Ambagudia, 2017). In general, political science and its many subdivisions are essential for comprehending the intricacies of politics, influencing policy, tackling social and political issues, and offering valuable perspectives on the choices and decisions made by people and society in the political realm. Political science and its sub-disciplines are essential for understanding the intricate nature of politics and its societal implications. In summary, political science and its sub-disciplines play a vital role in comprehending the complexities of politics, influencing policy-making, tackling social and political issues, and offering valuable insights into the choices and decisions made by individuals and societies in the political realm. The study of political science and its many sub-disciplines is crucial for comprehending political ideas, mechanisms, and advancements within society. In addition, they provide valuable contributions to the advancement of research methodologies and processes, using knowledge from several fields like economics, sociology, psychology, and statistics. In addition, political science and its sub-branches use interdisciplinary methods that integrate knowledge from history, philosophy, law, and geography to provide a thorough comprehension of the political environment (Chanthamith et al., 2019). Political science and its sub-disciplines are essential for comprehending the intricacies of politics, influencing policy, tackling social and political issues, and gaining awareness into the choices and decisions made by people and society in the political realm. The need of precise weather predictions in today's dynamic environment cannot be overemphasized. Accurate weather predictions are crucial, and political science and its sub-branches are essential for examining and comprehending significant political ideas, processes, and advancements.

Importance of Political Science and its Interdisciplinary Nature

CURRENT SCIENCE

Political science and its many sub-disciplines are crucial for comprehending political ideas, procedures, and advancements throughout society (Ambagudia, 2017). They provide significant perspectives on the operation of the state, government, constitution, political parties, citizenship, rights, liberty, equality, justice, power, and other related topics. Moreover, political science enhances comprehension of crucial elements such as the process of establishing democracy and the settlement of conflicts. These ideas and procedures are not only important for society, but also have a vital function in the advancement of the profession. Furthermore, political science and its several sub-disciplines has a strong interdisciplinary character. They use knowledge from several fields like economics, sociology, psychology, and statistics to design research methodologies and strategies. Interdisciplinary techniques enable political scientists to acquire a broad comprehension of the political environment and provide vital insights into the social, economic, psychological, and historical elements that impact politics. The multidisciplinary aspect of political science enables a comprehensive understanding of political phenomena. Political sociology investigates the interplay between politics and society, using sociological ideas and methodologies to comprehend how social elements influence political conduct and vice versa. Moreover, the multidisciplinary character of political science facilitates a more sophisticated comprehension of intricate matters like climate change. Political scientists can enhance the comprehension of climate change by scrutinizing the overarching dynamics of global governance, investigating public opinion and communication frameworks, analyzing political ecology and social geography, and delving into the psychological determinants that shape attitudes and behaviors pertaining to climate change.

The Importance of Human Lives and Choices in Political Science

The field of political science is primarily concerned with comprehending the repercussions of political choices and behaviors on the lives of individuals. Political science is to examine the impact of political systems and institutions on the lives of people and communities. This include the examination of power distribution, the implementation of authority, and the consequences of policies on various societal groups. Political scientists study the impact of political actions on the welfare and rights of individuals, as well as the overall social and economic

CURRENT SCIENCE

circumstances in which people reside. Through the study of political science, we get a deep understanding of the intricate systems and forces that shape human existence and decision-making. We have the capacity to analyze how political choices, strategies, and activities may either facilitate or impede social advancement, economic growth, parity, fairness, and human rights. Political science enables us to comprehend the intricacies of political systems and institutions, as well as to develop a deeper understanding of how politics influences our lives and how our individual and collective decisions may change the political environment. The study of political science is vital because it helps us understand how power is allocated and exercised, how choices are made, and how policies are implemented. Moreover, political science enables us to rigorously examine and assess the efficacy of various political systems, policies, and tactics in advancing societal objectives and tackling urgent social problems. Having this comprehension is crucial for making well-informed choices as individuals and engaging in democratic procedures. Political science is crucial for comprehending the interdependence between politics and human existence, as well as the importance of personal and collective decisions in molding the political environment and the general welfare of society. Political science is not the only field that contributes to comprehending the many problems and obstacles associated with climate change; other scientific disciplines also have a significant impact. Environmental science enables us to comprehend the repercussions of our actions on the environment and furnishes essential data and analysis about climate change. Political science, when combined with other scientific disciplines, is essential for comprehending and tackling the intricate difficulties that societies encounter, such as climate change. To summarize, political science is a multifaceted study that spans a range of areas and incorporates knowledge from other social sciences and academic fields. The disciplines included under the field of Political Science are political history, political psychology, political communication, political sociology, political economics, and other related areas (Refurbishing the curriculum for Political Science course, 2021). To summarize, political science is a multifaceted topic that spans a range of areas and incorporates knowledge from other social sciences and fields like economics, sociology, psychology, statistics, applied mathematics, history, philosophy, law, psychology, and geography. In addition to its multidisciplinary character, political science also adds to the knowledge of concepts such as state, government, constitution, political parties, citizenship, rights and duties, political ideologies, international relations, and more. Political

CURRENT SCIENCE

science is an ever-changing and multidisciplinary area of study that offers useful perspectives on politics, authority, the process of making decisions, and the execution of policies. It facilitates the meticulous examination and assessment of various political systems, policies, and methods in advancing societal objectives and tackling urgent social concerns. Political science is crucial in facilitating the democracy process, resolving conflicts, and analyzing political advancements. Additionally, it aids in comprehending and tackling the difficulties presented by climate change, as well as the manner in which governmental structures and social connections impact the standing of scientific understanding in this domain. The need of precise weather predictions in today's dynamic environment cannot be overemphasized. The need of precise weather predictions in today's dynamic environment cannot be overemphasized. The importance of political science and its incorporation with other scientific fields, such as climate science, in the current dynamic global landscape cannot be emphasized enough. The integration of political science with other scientific fields, such as climate science, is essential for comprehending and tackling the intricate issues that societies encounter, including climate change, social injustice, globalization, and political instability (Lahsen, 2010). In addition, political science encompasses not only the academic comprehension of politics but also the application of actual solutions to problems. Political science is crucial in providing information for policy choices and facilitating efficient government. It assists policymakers and government officials in making well-informed choices by using data, research, and analysis. Additionally, it plays a role in the development of political philosophy and the promotion of democratic ideas and practices. To summarize, political science is a complex field that includes several branches and connects with other scientific fields. To summarize, political science is a complex field that includes several branches and overlaps with other scientific areas. To summarize, political science is a complex field that includes several branches and connects with other scientific fields. The importance of political science and its incorporation with other scientific fields, such as climate science, in the fast-evolving contemporary world cannot be exaggerated. Political science not only deepens our comprehension of politics, but it also plays a pivotal role in tackling intricate social difficulties and guiding policy choices. The importance of political science and its incorporation with other scientific fields, such as climate science, in the current dynamic global landscape cannot be exaggerated. Political science plays a crucial role in comprehending the societal, economic, and political consequences of climate change and

CURRENT SCIENCE

developing efficient approaches for adapting to and reducing its impact. Moreover, via the analysis of the dynamic relationship among politics, power, and policy-making, political science offers significant perspectives on how governments and institutions can effectively tackle urgent issues such as social inequality, globalization, and political instability. Political science is crucial for comprehending and tackling real-world issues and formulating policies that may successfully confront social concerns. Political science, being an interdisciplinary domain, provides significant understanding of the intricate dynamics among politics, society, and human decision-making. Studying this subject enables us to comprehend the intricacies of power, governance, and decision-making, and its influence on our communities. Political science is an essential field of study that enhances our comprehension of politics and society, guides policy-making, and tackles urgent social, economic, and political issues. The importance of political science and its incorporation with other scientific fields is of utmost relevance in the current era of fast change. Political science, being a versatile and multidisciplinary field, has a vital function in comprehending and tackling intricate social issues in our swiftly evolving planet. Political science not only deepens our comprehension of politics, but it also serves a pivotal function in tackling intricate social issues and guiding policy choices. The importance of political science and its incorporation with other scientific fields cannot be exaggerated in the current dynamic global landscape. Political science, via its different sub-branches and multidisciplinary partnerships, provides vital insights into the linkages between politics, society, and human behavior. This paradigm facilitates the analysis and comprehension of political processes, institutions, and behavior. It assists in navigating the intricacies of governance and decision-making. The importance of political science in the contemporary world stems from its capacity to provide a thorough comprehension of politics, society, and human behavior in the midst of fast transformations. Political science not only provides us with a deeper understanding of the political landscape, but it also plays a crucial role in formulating efficient policies and methods to tackle social problems and obstacles. In summary, the study of political science is crucial for comprehending and resolving practical issues. It enables us to analyze the intricacies of power, governance, and decision-making, and provides insights for policy choices that may efficiently tackle social concerns. Political science is an essential field of study that enhances our comprehension of politics and society, guides policy-making, and tackles urgent social, economic, and political issues. The importance of political science and its

CURRENT SCIENCE

incorporation with other scientific fields is of utmost relevance in the current era of fast change. Political science plays a crucial role in comprehending and tackling practical political and social problems. Political science, with its many sub-disciplines and multidisciplinary partnerships, provides essential understanding of the connections among politics, society, and human conduct. This paradigm facilitates the analysis of political processes, institutions, and behavior, enabling us to effectively traverse the intricacies of governance and decision-making. Political science is essential in tackling intricate social issues and guiding policy choices in our fast-evolving environment. It enables us to comprehend the intricacies of power relations, the impact of institutions, and the underlying impulses driving political conduct. Furthermore, the incorporation of political science with other fields such as economics, sociology, psychology, and geography amplifies its capacity to provide a thorough comprehension of political processes and their influence on society (Chanthamith et al., 2019). Political science is an academic field that utilizes diverse methodologies and information from different social sciences to examine political phenomena (Morton & Williams, 2009). Political science, with its several sub-branches and multidisciplinary partnerships, provides vital insights into the intricate dynamics of politics, society, and human behavior. It is a crucial field of study for comprehending and tackling practical political and social problems.

Political science is an essential and multidisciplinary field that enhances our understanding of politics, society, and human behavior. This information offers useful perspectives on the mechanisms of authority, administration, and the process of making choices, and it helps shape policy decisions that may successfully tackle social difficulties. Political science is essential for tackling intricate social problems and providing guidance for policy choices. Political science aids in understanding the intricacies of government and offers a structure for examining political processes, institutions, and behavior. Moreover, the incorporation of political science with other fields like economics, sociology, psychology, and geography strengthens its capacity to provide a thorough comprehension of political processes and their influence on society (Chanthamith et al., 2019). In essence, political science transcends mere academic endeavor and has significant consequences and importance in the actual world. Political science aids in comprehending the world we inhabit and equips us with methods for scrutinizing and comprehending political procedures, establishments, and conduct. The ability to make well-informed choices, influence policy, and work towards a fair and equitable society is facilitated

CURRENT SCIENCE

by this. Political science is an academic field that utilizes diverse methodologies and expertise from different social sciences to examine political phenomena (Morton & Williams, 2009). Political science, with its several sub-branches and multidisciplinary cooperation, provides vital insights into the intricate nature of politics, society, and human behavior.

Implications and Importance of Political Science

The ramifications and significance of political science are extensive. Through the study of politics, we get a more profound comprehension of the intricacies of power relations, the mechanisms of decision-making, and the societal frameworks that influence our existence. Acquiring this information is essential for people, communities, and governments to successfully traverse the intricacies of political systems and actively engage in democratic processes. Political science is essential for advancing effective governance, safeguarding human rights and civil freedoms, and promoting social fairness. Moreover, political science functions as a mechanism for examining and resolving social problems, such as disparities, destitution, ecological concerns, and disputes. It assists us in discerning the fundamental reasons behind these difficulties and formulating efficient approaches for alleviation. Furthermore, political science enhances the advancement of public policy via the provision of study and analysis based on empirical data. This study provides valuable insights to politicians and campaigners, enabling them to make well-informed choices and develop policies that effectively meet the needs and aspirations of society. In essence, political science serves as an intermediary between theoretical concepts and practical applications, offering useful perspectives on the intricacies of politics and society. It provides a structure for comprehending the complexities of governance, political systems, and policy-making procedures. Through the study of political science, people acquire essential skills in critical thinking, analytical reasoning, and a more comprehensive understanding of social matters. These abilities and knowledge are advantageous not just for jobs in politics, government, and international affairs but also for a diverse array of professions including law, education, media, public administration, and advocacy. Hence, political science has both scholarly importance and tangible consequences in molding our global environment and influencing our personal and

CURRENT SCIENCE

societal decisions. Reference: "The Significance of Political Science in Contemporary Society", International Political Science Association. Political science is a complex field that includes several sub-disciplines and intersects with other scientific disciplines. Political science is a complex field that includes several sub-disciplines and intersects with other sciences, enabling a thorough comprehension of the frameworks that mold political systems and the variables that impact them. Additionally, it plays a key role in advancing good governance, safeguarding human rights and civil liberties, and cultivating social justice. This underscores the multidisciplinary character of political science and its importance in tackling social issues. Moreover, political science offers a structure for examining and comprehending the intricacies of human conduct, the processes of decision-making, and the distribution of resources within a political setting. To summarize, political science is an essential area of academic inquiry that covers several sub-disciplines and has interdisciplinary linkages with other scientific fields. Comprehending politics, governance, and social concerns is crucial, and its practical applications span across several professional domains. In general, political science is a significant field of study that delves into the intricacies of politics and society. Moreover, political science enhances societal progress via its provision of profound understanding of political occurrences, formulation of public policies, and cultivation of democratic principles. Political science is a multifaceted and linked subject that utilizes multiple fields of study to comprehend and tackle political problems. Political science provides us with information and comprehension of the structures, processes, and dynamics of politics in our society. Political science is both intellectually important and has tangible effects on the way we shape our society and the decisions we make as members of it. Humans. Political science is a multifaceted and linked subject that utilizes multiple fields of study to comprehend and tackle political problems. Political science is a multifaceted and linked subject that utilizes multiple fields of study to comprehend and tackle political problems. Political science is a multidisciplinary study that utilizes multiple disciplines to comprehend and tackle political events. Political science is a multifaceted and linked subject that utilizes multiple fields of study to comprehend and tackle political problems. Political science is a multifaceted and linked subject that utilizes multiple fields of study to comprehend and tackle political problems. Political science is essential for examining and understanding the intricacies of politics and social issues. It has a substantial

CURRENT SCIENCE

impact on the formation of public policy and the promotion of democratic principles. Political science is vital for comprehending the intricacies of politics, government, and social matters.

Interdisciplinary Approach in Political Science

Political science employs an interdisciplinary methodology by incorporating insights from other fields such as economics, sociology, psychology, and statistics. By using an interdisciplinary perspective, political scientists may use several methodological strategies to address substantive inquiries and get a more holistic understanding of political events. Political scientists use economic theories and models to examine the effects of policies on economic results, or employ sociological ideas to investigate the impact of social structures on political conduct. Moreover, the multidisciplinary character of political science allows researchers to analyze the interconnectedness of politics with many domains of human existence. Political sociology investigates the connection between politics and society, analyzing how social elements influence political conduct and establishments. Furthermore, political psychology investigates the psychological elements that impact the process of making decisions and engaging in political activities. In general, the interdisciplinary aspect of political science improves its capacity to examine and understand the intricacies of politics and social matters by integrating perspectives from many disciplines. The Significance of Political Science in Human Existence and Decision-Making The study of political science is crucial in human existence and decision-making since it enables people to comprehend the political mechanisms that influence their lives. Through the study of political science, people may get a comprehensive understanding of power distribution, policy-making processes, and institutional functioning. Having this information enables people to make well-informed choices about their political engagement, comprehend the consequences of various policies, and advocate for modifications that are in line with their beliefs and interests. Political science also provides students with crucial critical thinking and analytical abilities that are applicable to many careers and civic actions. Moreover, political science is essential in fostering effective government and tackling social challenges. Political scientists has the ability to provide useful perspectives and suggestions on policy issues, contribute to the creation of efficient and all-encompassing

CURRENT SCIENCE

systems of government, and assess the consequences of political choices on society. Political science is an interdisciplinary domain that utilizes a range of social and scientific disciplines to examine political behavior, institutions, and processes. Comprehending the intricacies of politics is essential for making well-informed choices about political engagement. The multidisciplinary aspect of political science facilitates a holistic comprehension of politics and its influence on human existence and decision-making. Political science sub-branches, such as political sociology and political psychology, investigate the connections between politics and many aspects of human life and behavior (Chanthamith et al., 2019). These sub-branches elucidate the social, psychological, and geographical elements that impact political behavior and decision-making. Moreover, the multidisciplinary character of political science facilitates a thorough comprehension of politics and its influence on human existence and decisions. Political science achieves a comprehensive understanding of the political processes and factors that form our societies by incorporating ideas from economics, sociology, psychology, and other disciplines. Hence, political science is crucial not only for comprehending politics per se, but also for grasping the interdependence of politics with other facets of human existence. The integration of political science with other disciplines significantly amplifies the depth and significance of the subject, enabling a more profound examination of political issues. Furthermore, the several subdivisions of political science, such as political history and political economics, enhance our comprehension of the historical and economic elements that influence political choices and results. Political science is an essential field of study that investigates the many dimensions of politics and its interconnections with other scientific disciplines. It offers useful perspectives on policy issues, enhances the establishment of efficient governance systems, evaluates the consequences of political choices on society, and deepens our comprehension of the intricacies of political conduct and decision-making. The importance of precise weather predictions in today's dynamic environment cannot be exaggerated. Hence, the examination of political science and its subsidiary fields is crucial for grasping the intricacies of politics, comprehending the elements that sway political conduct and decision-making, and ultimately formulating well-informed and efficient policies that directly affect human existence and choices. The field of political science, together with its sub-disciplines including political sociology and political psychology, is essential for comprehending the interconnections between politics and many aspects of human existence and conduct. In general, political science

CURRENT SCIENCE

and its many subdivisions provide significant perspectives on the workings of politics and its influence on human lives and decisions. Moreover, political science enables us to comprehend the influence of power and governance in molding communities, organizations, and people. Through the examination of political science and its many sub-disciplines, we may get a thorough comprehension of the intricacies of politics and its interrelations with other scientific fields. The multidisciplinary approach is crucial as it enables a comprehensive comprehension of political occurrences and their wider ramifications. To summarize, political science and its sub-disciplines constitute a crucial and multidisciplinary area of academic inquiry. They enhance our comprehension of politics, its interconnections with other disciplines, and its effects on human existence and decision-making. The study of political science and its sub-branches is crucial in our fast-paced world. It allows us to grasp the intricacies of politics, comprehend the influences on political behavior and decision-making, and ultimately develop well-informed and impactful policies that directly affect human life and choices. Political science and its many subdivisions are essential for comprehending political conduct, the process of making choices, and the influence of politics on society. Moreover, the field of political science and its many subdivisions provide significant perspectives on the intricacies of political systems and their influence on human existence and decision-making. Studying political science and its sub-branches is crucial for comprehending the intricacies of politics, examining the determinants of political behavior and decision-making, and ultimately formulating well-informed and efficient policies that directly affect human life and choices. Political science and its sub-branches are essential for understanding the intricacies of politics, analyzing the determinants of political behavior and decision-making, and formulating well-informed policies that have a significant effect on human lives and choices. The study of political science and its sub-branches is crucial in order to grasp the intricacies of politics, analyze the determinants that influence governance and power dynamics, and appreciate the consequences of politics on societies, institutions, and people in our fast-evolving world. Political science and its sub-disciplines are crucial for comprehending the intricacies of politics, examining the determinants that influence political conduct and decision-making, and eventually formulating well-informed and efficacious policies that may profoundly influence human lives and choices.

CURRENT SCIENCE

Conclusion

The field of political science, together with its several sub-disciplines, is essential for understanding the intricacies of politics, analyzing the determinants of political behavior and decision-making, and eventually formulating well-informed and impactful policies that directly affect human lives and choices. Ultimately, the study of political science and its sub-branches is crucial for understanding the complexities of politics, analyzing the diverse factors that shape political behavior and decision-making, and ultimately formulating well-informed and impactful policies that directly affect human life and choices. The study of political science and its sub-branches is essential for comprehending political behavior, decision-making, and the influence of politics on human lives and choices in our fast-evolving world. Political science and its sub-disciplines are crucial for comprehending the intricacies of politics, examining the determinants of political behavior and decision-making, and eventually formulating well-informed and efficacious policies that directly affect human lives and choices. (Updating the curriculum for the Political Science course, 2021). Political science and its sub-branches are essential for grasping the intricacies of politics, appreciating the determinants of political behavior and decision-making, and formulating well-informed policies that have an effect on human lives and choices. The study of political science and its sub-branches is crucial for comprehending the intricacies of politics, examining the determinants of political behavior and decision-making, and ultimately formulating well-informed and impactful policies that directly affect human life and choices in our rapidly evolving world. The study of political science and its sub-branches allows us to acquire a more profound comprehension of power dynamics, the functioning of governments, and the processes involved in making political choices.

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